

A Simple Method for Regeneration of Steroidal Ketones from their Oximes

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A simple method of deoxygenation of steroidal ketoximes has been described. This involves the 'reductive hydrolysis' of a ketoxime with zinc-acetic acid-water system. Both the saturated as well as, $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated steroidal ketoximes undergo ready deoxygenation. Mechanism of zinc-acetic acid reduction of steroidal vinyl nitro compounds has been discussed.

A number of methods are known for recovering ketones from their semicarbazones and oximes. These include (a) acid-catalysed hydrolysis¹, (b) exchange reaction with pyruvic acid², levulinic acid³, and formaldehyde⁴ and (c) treatment with nitrous acid⁵.

A survey of literature revealed that semicarbazones are more useful as derivatives for the separation of steroidal ketones than the corresponding oximes. This is apparently because of the greater difficulty encountered in the regeneration of steroidal ketones from their oximes².

In connection with our work in the field of steroids we were concerned with the preparation of steroidal-6-ketones and their oximes. The ketones are conveniently obtained by the zinc-acetic acid reduction of the corresponding vinyl nitro compounds⁶. (Equation I).

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4. J. A. Barltrop, A. J. Johnson and G. D. Meakins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 181.
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6. C. E. Anagnostopoulos and L. F. Fieser, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 532.

The oximes could be obtained either from the corresponding ketones by conventional method or by controlled reduction of the vinyl nitro compounds of 7,⁸. We made attempts to work out the optimum conditions for converting the nitro compounds into oximes by zinc-acetic acid method. It was found that the reduction even under mild conditions invariably gave a mixture of ketone and oxime, the relative amounts of the two depending upon the reaction conditions. Apparently, the oximes initially formed suffered ready 'reductive hydrolysis' to give the ketones (table I). In a recent publication Kaye,

TABLE I

Zinc—Acetic Acid reduction of Steroidal Nitro compounds

S. No.	Compound/g	Experimental conditions					g	Ketone* %	g	Oxime* %	
		Zn/g	Water /ml	Acetic acid /ml	Bath temp. °C	Time /hr.					
1.	3β-Acetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene ⁶	1.0	2	2	20	60-65	1/2	0.45	48.8	0.212	21.9
2.	„	„	„	„	„	„	1	0.525	56.17	0.181	18.7
3.	„	„	„	„	„	„	2	0.599	64.1	0.165	17.0
4.	„	„	„	„	„	„	3	0.73	78.1	0.03	3.1
5.	3β-Chloro-6-nitrocholest-5-ene ⁸ .	1.0	„	„	„	„	2	0.56	60.1	0.075	7.8
6.	6-Nitrocholest-5-ene ¹³	1.0	„	„	„	„	2	0.51	54.9	0.125	13.0

*Chromatographic separation and yields reported after one crystallization.

Weiss and Hight⁸ have suggested that the oximes are the direct precursors of the ketones in these reductions (Equation II). This is in contrast to the previously described mechanism⁹ where imines are involved as the precursor of the ketones.

We have found that the steroidal oximes (which we have studied so far) do not suffer hydrolysis if simply heated with acetic acid-water mixture as suggested by Kaye et al. (table II).

7. T. Mitui, *Chem. Abst.*, 1941, **35**, 4390.
8. I. K. Kaye, U. Weiss and R. J. Hight, *Steroids*, 1966, **8**(1), 1.
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The sensitivity of a steroidal ketoxime towards zinc acetic acid-water mixture (and not towards acetic acid and water) strongly suggests that the oxime is further reduced presumably to imine and then the latter undergoes hydrolytic cleavage to give the ketone. (Equation III).

TABLE II

Attempted Hydrolysis of Steroidal Ketoximes with Acetic Acid and Water.

S. No.	Compound/g	Water/ml	Acetic acid/ml	Bath temp.°C	Time/hr.	Oxime* g	recovered %
1.	3 β -Acetoxycholestan-6-one oxime ¹⁰ 1.0	2	20	95-100	2	0.939	94
2.	3 β -Chlorocholestan-6-one oxime. ¹² 1.0	„	„	„	„	0.902	90
3.	Cholestan-3-one oxime ¹⁵ 1.0	„	„	„	„	0.85	85
4.	3 β -Acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one oxime ¹⁷ 1.0	„	„	„	„	0.9	90
5.	Cholest-5-en-7-one oxime ¹⁸ 1.0	„	„	„	„	0.924	92

*yields reported after one crystallisation.

These observations opened up the possibility that oximes as a class may be conveniently converted into the corresponding ketones if subjected to reductive hydrolysis. With this view in mind we subjected various steroidal ketoximes to zinc-acetic acid-water reduction and have found that the ketones are obtained in high yields. Both the saturated as well as the α,β -unsaturated steroidal ketoximes were found to regenerate ketones by this method (Table III).

TABLE III

Reductive Hydrolysis of Steroidal Ketoximes

S. No.	Compounds/g	Experimental conditions					Ketone*	
		Zn/g	Water/ml	Acetic acid/ml	Bath temp.°C	Time/hr.	g	%
1.	3 β -Acetoxycholestan-6-one oxime ¹⁰ 1.0	2	2	20	95-100	1.5	3 β -Acetoxycholestan-6-one ⁶ 0.640	66.1
2.	3- β Chlorocholestan-6-one oxime ¹² 1.0	„	„	„	„	2	3 β -Chlorocholestan-6-one ¹¹ 0.632	65.5

TABLE III (Contd)

S.No.	Compounds/ g	Experimental Conditions					Time/hr.	Ketone*	
		Zn/g	Water/ml	Acetic acid/ml	Bath temp.°C	g		%	
3.	Cholestan-3-one-oxime ¹⁵	2	2	20	95-100	2	Cholestan-3-one ¹⁶		
	1.0	„	„	„	„	„	0.628	65.24	
4.	3 β -Acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one oxime ¹⁷	„	„	„	„	„	3 β -Acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one ¹⁹		
	1.0	„	„	„	„	„	0.620	63.93	
5.	Cholest-5-en-7-one oxime ¹⁸	„	„	„	„	„	Cholest-5-en-7-one ²⁰		
	1.0	„	„	„	„	„	0.687	71.37	
6.	Cholestan-6-one oxime ¹⁴	„	„	„	„	„	Cholestan-6-one ¹³		
	1.0	„	„	„	„	„	0.630	65.46	
7.	Cholest-4-en-3-one oxime ²¹	„	„	„	„	„	Cholest-4-en-3-one ²¹		
	1.0	„	„	„	„	„	0.520	54.03	

*Chromatographic separation and yields reported after one crystallisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the steroidal compounds described were prepared by standard methods. Details of only typical experiments are being given.

Section 'A'

Zinc-Acetic acid reduction of steroidal nitro compounds.

1. 3 β -Acetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1.0 g; m.p. 103°)⁶ was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and to this zinc powder (2.0 g) and water (2.0 ml) were added. The reaction mixture was warmed on a water-bath (60-65°) for 1/2 hr, and then poured in crushed ice-water mixture and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and water and dried (sodium sulphate). The crude material obtained after the removal of solvent was chromatographed over neutral alumina (25.0 g; Brockmann Grade I). Elution with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (2 : 1) gave 3 β -acetoxycholestan-6-one⁶, crystallized from ethanol (0.45 g; 48.8%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 129-130°. Further elution with benzene-ether (1 : 1) gave 3 β -acetoxycholestan-6-one oxime¹⁰, crystallized from ethanol (0.212 g; 22%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 201-202°.

2. A mixture of 3 β -chloro-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1.0 g; m.p. 149°)⁸, acetic acid (20 ml), zinc (2.0 g) and water (2.0 ml) was warmed on a water bath (60-65°) for 2 hr. It was worked up as described earlier and the crude material chromatographed over neutral alumina (25.0 g). Elution with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (2 : 1) gave 3 β -chloro-

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17. H. J. Eckhardt, *Ber.*, 1938, **71**, 461.

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19. A. Windaus, H. Lettre and Fr. Schenck, *Ann.*, 1935, **520**, 98.

20. W. G. Dauben and K. H. Takemura, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 6302.

21. C. W. Shoppee, G. Kruger and R. N. Mirrington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1050.

cholestan-6-one¹¹, crystallized from methanol (0.56 g, 60%)** m.p. and mixed m.p. 129-130°. Further elution with benzene-ether (1 : 1) gave 3 β -Chlorocholestan-6-one oxime¹², crystallized from ethanol (75 mg; 7.8%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 174-175°.

Section 'B' : Attempted hydrolysis of steroidal keto oximes with acetic acid and water.

1. 3 β -Acetoxycholestan-6-one oxime (1.0 g; m.p. 201-202°)¹⁰ was dissolved in acetic acid (20 ml) and water (2.0 ml) and the clear solution was heated on a water bath (95-100°) for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with large excess of cold water and extracted with ether. After usual work up the residue was crystallized from ethanol to give the unchanged oxime (0.939 g; 94%) m.p. and mixed m.p. 200-202°.

2. A mixture of 3 β -Chlorocholestan-6-one oxime (1.0 g; m.p. 175°)¹², acetic acid (20 ml) and water (2.0 ml) was heated on a water bath for 2 hr. After usual work up the unchanged oxime was recovered, which was crystallized from ethanol (0.902 g; 90%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 174-175°.

Section 'C' : Reductive hydrolysis of steroidal keto oximes :

1. A mixture of 3 β -Acetoxycholestan-6-one oxime (1.0 g; m.p. 201-202°)¹⁰, acetic acid (20 ml), water (2.0 ml) and zinc powder (2.0 g) was heated on a water bath (95-100°) for 1.5 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up in the manner described earlier for nitro compounds. The crude material thus obtained was chromatographed over neutral alumina (25 g). Elution with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (2:1) and benzene afforded 3 β -acetoxycholestan-6-one⁶, crystallized from ethanol (0.64 g; 66%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 128-129°.

2. 3 β -Chlorocholestan-6-one oxime (1.0 g; m.p. 175°)¹² was deoximated under similar conditions. The crude product was chromatographed; the eluates from petroleum ether-benzene (2 : 1) and benzene furnished 3 β -Chlorocholestan-6-one¹¹, recrystallized from ethanol (0.632 g; 65.5%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 129-130°.

3. Cholest-5-en-7-one oxime (1.0 g; m.p. 177-180°)¹⁸ was subjected to the above treatment. The crude product was chromatographed; the eluates from petroleum ether (60-80°) and benzene(2:1) and benzene gave cholest-5-en-7-one²⁰ crystallized from ethanol (0.687 g; 71.4%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 153-154°.

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**It is interesting to note that 3,5-Cyclocholestan-6-one as reported earlier⁸ was not obtained by us in this experiment.